

A study on the correlation between hydrographical features and Microalgae abundance at Sri Uma Kotilingeswara Swami temple stream, Punyagiri, S.Kota, Vizianagaram, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Padmaja Rani Ponnaganti^{1*}, P. K. Ratna Kumar²

^{1*}, ² Dept. of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam 530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Monitoring microalgae is crucial for assessing water quality in aquatic environments, as it provides insights into the fundamental characteristics and ecological balance of these systems. Microalgae are essential indicators of species abundance and health in freshwater ecosystems. This study aimed to examine the correlation between microalgae abundance and hydrographical parameters air temperature, water temperature, rainfall, humidity, and wind at the Punyagiri Hills near S. Kota in Vizianagaram, Andhra Pradesh, over three years from May 2018 to April 2021. The results indicated that Chlorophyceae were the most prevalent group, constituting 57% of the total microalgal community, with 35 genera and 61 species identified. Bacillariophyceae represented 25% of the community, comprising 17 genera and 32 species. Cyanophyceae accounted for 12%, with 14 genera and 25 species, while Euglenophyceae made up 6%, with 4 genera and 9 species. The study found that air and water temperature, as well as wind, had a significant positive correlation with Bacillariophyceae abundance. In contrast, rainfall and humidity showed a positive correlation with the abundance of Chlorophyceae, Cyanophyceae, and Euglenophyceae.

Keywords: Hydrographic parameters, Phytoplankton abundance, Correlation, Punyagiri, Andhra Pradesh

INTRODUCTION

Environmental conditions and seasonal variations significantly influence natural ecosystems, particularly aquatic systems, which are sensitive to climatic factors such as physical, chemical, and biological components (Ingole et al., 2010). The interplay of hydrographical features including seasonal transitions, air and water temperature fluctuations, rainfall patterns, humidity levels, wind dynamics, and nutrient cycles critically determines the dominance of algae within these ecosystems (Harikrishna et al., 1999; Varsha, 2019). In freshwater

environments, microalgae, which serve as primary producers in the ecological food chain, are essential in maintaining the health and balance of aquatic species (Pradhan, 2023). These microalgae are particularly abundant in slower-moving streams compared to fast-flowing rivers, as they tend to grow on submerged rocks and mud, contributing to the stability of the aquatic system.

Microalgae's diverse capabilities make them invaluable for ecological assessments of water bodies such as lakes,

ponds, reservoirs, rivers, and streams, where they are used as indicators of water quality (Bharathi and Hosmani, 1973). Significant research has been conducted on the freshwater phytoplankton of Andhra Pradesh, India, highlighting the region's rich biodiversity (Munawar, 1970; Kodarkar, 1995; Jyothi & Narasimha Rao, 2013a, 2013b; Bhanu Prakash et al., 2014; Jyotsna et al., 2015; Setu et al., 2015). Further studies have examined the seasonal variations of microalgae and their correlation with hydrographical features throughout the year (Tiwari & Shukla,

2007; Smita et al., 2010). The current study focused on analyzing the seasonal variation of microalgae and their relationship with hydrographical conditions in the Punyagiri temple stream, S. Kota Mandal, Vizianagaram district, over three years from May 2018 to April 2021. The research aimed to elucidate the interrelationship between microalgae and the hydrographical features of the Punyagiri Hills' temple stream, providing valuable insights into the ecological dynamics of this region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

A comprehensive study on the seasonal variations of microalgae in the temple stream of Punyagiri Hills was conducted over three years from May 2018 to April 2021. The Punyagiri hills, situated 4 km from S. Kota and 62 km from Visakhapatnam, house the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara Swami Temple, a renowned religious site. The geographical coordinates of the temple stream are 18°11'19" N latitude and 83°11'19" E longitude. The region is characterized by several perennial streams that provide a stable aquatic environment, fostering the growth and development of diverse microalgal communities (Figure 1). These streams, sustained throughout the year by natural springs, create an ideal habitat for studying the temporal changes in microalgal populations, reflecting the dynamic interactions between environmental factors and aquatic ecosystems in this unique geographical setting.

Figure 1: Water streams at Punyagiri Hills with microalgal Bloom blooms

Collection of Samples

Water samples were systematically collected from three distinct locations within the temple stream of Punyagiri Hills, with sampling points spaced 10 meters apart to ensure representative coverage. The sampling sites were strategically positioned in the middle of the stream to capture the central flow, which is likely to contain a diverse range of microalgae. Algal samples were carefully gathered using forceps and a spatula, then transferred into plastic

containers containing 4% formalin to preserve the specimens for laboratory analysis. Air and water temperatures were recorded at the time of collection using a mercury-filled centigrade thermometer with an accuracy of 0.1°C, ensuring precise measurements. Other hydrographical parameters were analyzed following standard methods to assess the environmental conditions at each site.

In the laboratory, the collected samples were subjected to centrifugation at speeds of 1500-2000 rpm for 10-12 minutes to concentrate the algal cells. The settled algal biomass was then diluted to an optimal concentration that allowed for easy counting under a compound binocular microscope at magnifications of 10X and 40X. The abundance of phytoplankton was quantified by counting individual cells and multiplying by the appropriate dilution factor, following established protocols as outlined by APHA and described in the works of Welch (1948), Smith (1950), Trivedi and Goel (1986), Kodarkar et al. (1991), and Dhanapathi (2000). This rigorous methodological approach ensured accurate and reliable data on the composition and density of the microalgal communities present in the stream, contributing to a better understanding of their seasonal dynamics to the hydrographical features of the Punyagiri hills.

Phytoplankton analysis

The phytoplankton sample was carefully prepared for microscopic examination by placing it on a clean slide. Using a needle, the material was evenly spread across the slide to ensure a uniform layer. A drop of water was then added to the spread material to facilitate better visualization, and a coverslip was gently placed over the sample. The coverslip was lightly pressed with a thumb to remove any excess water droplets, ensuring a clear and stable preparation. The prepared slide was then examined under both high and low magnification using a compound microscope to observe the microalgal structures in detail.

The identification of the observed algal samples was conducted using standard reference literature. The microalgae were identified by consulting established monographs and manuals, which provided detailed descriptions and illustrations of various algal species. Key references used for this purpose included seminal works by Fritsch (1907), Desikachary (1959), Chapman (1962), Philipose (1960 and 1967), Prescott (1984), and Anand (1998). These authoritative sources allowed for accurate identification of the microalgal species present in the samples, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the phytoplankton diversity in the Punyagiri temple stream.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hydrographical features of the running water stream at Punyagiri Hill were systematically analyzed from May

2018 to April 2021, revealing significant seasonal variations. Temperature, a key factor influencing physical and chemical

reactions in aquatic ecosystems, showed considerable fluctuations. The surface water temperature exhibited significant variability, with the highest temperature of 33.80°C recorded in April, indicating the peak of pre-monsoon heat. The lowest surface water temperature, 20.2°C, was observed in January, reflecting the cooler winter months. Air temperatures followed a similar trend, peaking at 33.58°C in May and dipping to 22.54°C in December, indicating the influence of seasonal changes on both air and water temperatures (Figure 2A). These findings are consistent with previous studies by Salve and Hiware (2006), Aher et al. (2006), Sharma (2007), Kadam (2007), Chaudhari (2009), Javaid Ahmad and Ashok (2012), and Mahesh et al. (2013), who also observed significant temperature variations in similar aquatic environments. The water temperature exhibited similar patterns, with a maximum of 31.4°C recorded in May 2020 and a minimum of 15.8°C in December 2020 (Figure 2A).

Rainfall, another critical hydrographical parameter, showed a marked variation throughout the study period. Rainfall data indicated a pronounced monsoonal influence, with the highest precipitation recorded in September at 66.09 mm, signifying the peak of the monsoon season. In contrast, the driest period was observed in February, with a minimal rainfall of 0.9 mm. This clear demarcation between wet and dry seasons is critical for understanding the

hydrological dynamics of the stream and its impact on the surrounding ecosystem. (Figure 2B). Humidity levels in the region demonstrated a strong correlation with the monsoon cycle. The highest humidity was observed in September at 91.54%, consistent with the peak rainfall period. The lowest humidity, 22.77%, was recorded in May, during the pre-monsoon season, highlighting the arid conditions prevalent before the onset of the monsoon (Figure 2C).

Additionally, wind speed, which influences evaporation and the dispersal of microalgae, ranged from 19 km/h to 6 km/h across the study area. Wind speed data showed considerable variation throughout the year, with the highest speed of 18.73 km/h occurring in May, which may be attributed to the increased atmospheric pressure gradients during the pre-monsoon period. The lowest wind speed was 6.9 km/h, recorded in November, reflecting the calm conditions that typically follow the monsoon retreat (Figure 2D). These hydrographical features play a crucial role in shaping the ecological dynamics of the Punyagiri hill stream, affecting the distribution and abundance of microalgal communities over time. The data collected provide valuable insights into the complex interplay between environmental factors and aquatic life, contributing to a deeper understanding of the ecological processes in this unique freshwater ecosystem.

Figure 2: Hydrographical features of Sri Uma Koti Lingeswara Swami Temple Stream, S. Kota village, Vizianagaram District, Andhra Pradesh. A)Surface water temperatures, B) Rainfall, C) Humidity, and D) Wind speed

Distribution of Algae

The results presented in Table 1 provide a detailed account of the abundance and distribution of different algal classes in the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara temple stream from May 2018 to April 2021. The study reveals that the Chlorophyceae class was the most abundant, with the highest number

of organisms per liter recorded throughout the investigation period. This class demonstrated significant dominance in the algal community, indicating its adaptability and favorable conditions in the temple stream. In contrast, the Euglenophyceae class exhibited less variation in its distribution, with a relatively stable

number of organisms per liter over time, suggesting a consistent yet limited presence in the ecosystem.

The study identified a total of 135 species belonging to 69 genera and four major algal classes. Chlorophyceae emerged as the most diverse class, with 34 genera and 64 species, highlighting its ecological significance in the stream. Bacillariophyceae followed, with 17 genera and 36 species, while Cyanophyceae comprised 14 genera and 26 species. Euglenophyceae, though the least abundant, was represented by 4 genera and 9 species. The total microalgal abundance in the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara temple stream was recorded at 4460 organisms per milliliter, indicating a rich and diverse algal population in this freshwater habitat.

The hierarchy of microalgal dominance in the stream, based on organism per milliliter data, underscores the ecological dynamics at play in this aquatic system. Chlorophyceae's dominance reflects its adaptability to the environmental conditions prevalent in the temple stream, while the presence of Bacillariophyceae, Cyanophyceae, and Euglenophyceae adds to the overall biodiversity and stability of the microalgal community. This comprehensive assessment of algal diversity and abundance offers valuable insights into the health and ecological balance of the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara temple stream over the three-year study period.

Chlorophyceae >
Bacillariophyceae > Cyanophyceae >
Euglenophyceae

This study revealed a pronounced dominance of the Chlorophyceae group in the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara Swamy temple stream, significantly outnumbering other algal groups. Chlorophyceae, commonly known as green algae, exhibited a peak abundance of 255 organisms per milliliter (org/ml) in October and a minimum of 144 org/ml in April, contributing to 62.85% of the total microalgal population, with an average density of 2411 org/ml over the investigation period. The dominance of this group was particularly evident during the winter and summer seasons, a pattern consistent with findings by Sanap et al. (2008), Ravish and Singh (2010), and Setu and Rao (2016). The genera *Oedogonium*, *Microspora*, *Spirogyra*, *Ulothrix*, and *Zygnema* were notably prevalent, indicating the group's adaptability and ecological significance in this freshwater habitat.

Bacillariophyceae, or diatoms, constituted 28.95% of the total microalgal population in the stream, with a maximum density of 171 org/ml observed in April and a minimum of 42 org/ml in October. The genera *Cyclotella*, *Skeletonema*, *Cymbella*, *Navicula*, *Fragilaria*, *Pinnularia*, and *Synedra* were dominant during the study period, underscoring the importance of Bacillariophyceae as environmental indicators in freshwater ecosystems, as supported by research from Wijewardene et al. (2021) and Wu et al. (2017). The study highlights that the growth of Bacillariophyceae was closely tied to favorable environmental conditions, particularly air and water temperatures, which are crucial for the proliferation of this group in the aquatic ecosystem.

The Cyanophyceae group, commonly known as blue-green algae, accounted for 6.44% of the total microalgal population in the temple stream. This group reached its peak abundance in August with 70 org/ml and recorded a minimum density of 54 org/ml in April. Dominant genera within this group included *Chroococcus*, *Merismopedia*, *Oscillatoria*, *Spirulina*, *Anabaena*, *Rivularia*, and *Nostoc*. The study suggests that environmental factors such as rainfall and humidity were particularly conducive to the growth of Cyanophyceae, contributing to their seasonal abundance and distribution within the stream.

Euglenophyceae, although the least abundant group, represented 1.67% of the total phytoplankton population in the Punyagiri temple stream. The maximum density of Euglenophyceae was recorded in January at 23 org/ml, with the lowest counts of 11 org/ml observed in May and July. The genera *Euglena* and *Phacus* were prominent during the study period, and their growth was closely associated with hydrographical conditions such as rainfall, humidity, moderate temperatures, and the availability of nutrients. The presence of

these conditions during the winter months likely contributed to the observed peak in Euglenophyceae density.

The total phytoplankton population showed variation across the study period, with the highest overall abundance recorded in June (417 org/ml) and the lowest in July (261 org/ml). This variation suggests that seasonal changes, including temperature, light availability, and nutrient input, significantly influence phytoplankton dynamics in the stream. The results of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the seasonal dynamics and environmental preferences of different algal groups in the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara Swamy temple stream. The distinct dominance patterns and temporal variations in the abundance of Chlorophyceae, Bacillariophyceae, Cyanophyceae, and Euglenophyceae highlight the complex interplay between hydrographical conditions and algal ecology in this freshwater ecosystem. These findings are crucial for the ecological assessment and management of freshwater resources, particularly in regions with similar environmental conditions.

Table 1: Abundance of phytoplankton of Punyagiri temple stream during May 2018 to Apr 2021

Month	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Total	%
Chlorophyceae	144	235	152	234	236	255	244	235	182	152	153	149	2371	62.85
Bacillariophyceae	153	101	42	64	66	43	55	51	79	117	153	171	1095	28.95
Cyanophyceae	54	67	56	70	64	59	60	62	62	62	56	58	243	6.44
Euglenophyceae	11	14	11	20	21	21	17	19	23	20	19	12	63	1.67
Total	362	417	261	388	387	378	376	367	346	351	381	390	3772	100

Correlation between hydrographical features and density of phytoplankton

The study on the correlation between physical variables and phytoplankton abundance in the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara Swamy Temple Stream from May 2018 to April 2021 reveals distinct patterns in how different environmental factors influence phytoplankton groups (Table 2). Air temperature exhibited a positive correlation with Bacillariophyceae ($r = 0.04$), suggesting that variations in air temperature may slightly enhance the abundance of this group. Conversely, air temperature negatively correlated with Chlorophyceae ($-r = 0.19$), Cyanophyceae ($-r = 0.73$), and Euglenophyceae ($-r = 0.98$), indicating a potential inhibitory effect on these groups as air temperatures rise. This trend could reflect temperature sensitivity among these phytoplankton groups.

Water temperature demonstrated a positive correlation with Bacillariophyceae ($r = 0.37$), indicating that warmer water may support the growth of diatoms. However, it negatively correlated with Chlorophyceae ($-r = 0.91$), Cyanophyceae

($-r = 0.37$), and Euglenophyceae ($-r = 0.36$), suggesting that elevated water temperatures could adversely affect these groups. Rainfall showed a positive correlation with Chlorophyceae ($r = 0.23$), Cyanophyceae ($r = 0.28$), and Euglenophyceae ($r = 0.19$), which implies that increased precipitation may promote their growth, while Bacillariophyceae had a negative correlation with rainfall ($-r = 0.14$). Humidity was positively correlated with Chlorophyceae ($r = 0.03$), Cyanophyceae ($r = 0.16$), and Euglenophyceae ($r = 0.05$), yet negatively correlated with Bacillariophyceae ($-r = 0.88$), indicating that higher humidity might not support diatom abundance. Lastly, wind speed showed a strong positive correlation with Bacillariophyceae ($r = 0.86$), suggesting that higher wind speeds could benefit diatom populations. In contrast, wind had a negative impact on Chlorophyceae ($-r = 0.69$), Cyanophyceae ($-r = 0.72$), and Euglenophyceae ($-r = 0.82$), indicating that increased wind may hinder the growth of these phytoplankton groups. All correlations reported are highly significant at the $p < 0.01$ level,

underscoring the robustness of these relationships.

The data suggest that environmental variables have differential impacts on microalgal densities. Bacillariophyceae are positively correlated with water temperature and humidity, but negatively with wind speed.

Chlorophyceae and Cyanophyceae show varied responses to these environmental factors, with generally negative correlations with water temperature and wind speed. Euglenophyceae, on the other hand, exhibit a strong negative correlation with both air and water temperatures, indicating that these conditions are less favorable for their growth.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix among Physical Variables and Microalgal Density of Sri Uma Koti Lingeswara Swamy temple stream

Parameters	AT	WT	RF	HUM	WS	Chl	Bac	Cyn	Eug
AT	1								
WT	0.02	1							
RF	-0.44	0.28	1						
HUM	-0.52	-0.41	0.03	1					
WS	-0.72	0.05	0.82	0.86	1				
Chl	-0.19	-0.91	0.23	0.03	-0.69	1			
Bac	0.04	0.37	-0.14	0.88	-0.01	-0.69	1		
Cyn	-0.73	-0.37	-0.28	0.16	0.22	-0.01	-0.37	1	
Eug	-0.98	-0.36	0.19	0.05	-0.37	0.22	-0.17	-0.01	1

CONCLUSION

The current study reveals that the Punyagiri Temple stream is predominantly inhabited by members of the Chlorophyceae, followed by Bacillariophyceae, Cyanophyceae, and Euglenophyceae. A total of 135 species were identified, distributed across 69 genera and four classes. Specifically, Chlorophyceae was the most diverse class, comprising 34 genera and 64 species. Bacillariophyceae included 17 genera and 36 species, Cyanophyceae encompassed 14 genera and 26 species, and

Euglenophyceae was represented by 4 genera and 9 species. The overall microalgal abundance in the Sri Uma Kotilingeswara Temple stream was recorded at 3,772 organisms per milliliter. The study also found that air temperature, water temperature, and wind speed were positively correlated with Bacillariophyceae abundance, while rainfall and humidity showed a significant positive correlation with the abundance of Chlorophyceae, Cyanophyceae, and Euglenophyceae.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they hold no competing interests

Acknowledgments

The authors are thankful to the Head of the Department of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, the local people, and who helped me during the field studies at Punyagiri Temple Street.

References

- Aher, S. K., Mane, U. H., & Pawar, B. A. (2007). A study on physicochemical parameters of Kagdipura swamp in relation to pisciculture, near Aurangabad, Maharashtra. *Journal of Aquatic Biology*, 22(1), 93-96.
- Anand, N. (1998). *Indian freshwater microalgae*. Bishen Singh Mahendra Pal Singh.
- Bhanu Prakash, M., Jyothi, K., & Narasimha Rao, G. M. (2014). Seasonal variations of phytoplankton community structure in relation to physicochemical factors in Lake Kolleru, Andhra Pradesh. *Indian Journal of Algal Biomass Utilization*, 5(3), 1-7.
- Bharathi, S. G., & Hosmani, S. P. (1973). Hydrobiological studies in ponds and lakes of Dharwar (Yemmekeri Pond). *Karnataka University Journal of Science*, 18(1), 101-115.
- Chapman, V. J. (1962). *The algae*. Macmillan.
- Chaudhari, U. E. (2009). Assessment of water quality parameters in Shimbhora dam water. *Indian Journal of Environmental Ecoplan*, 16(2-3), 487-490.
- Desikachary, T. V. (1959). *Cyanophyta*. Indian Council of Agricultural Research.
- Dhanapathi, M. V. S. S. S. (2000). *Taxonomic notes on the Rotifers from India (1889-2000)*. Indian Association of Aquatic Biologists (IAAB).
- Frisch, F. E. (1907). The sub-aerial and freshwater algae flora of the tropics. *Annals of Botany*, 21(1), 235-275.
- Harikrishna, K., Sabu, T., Snail, G., Paul, M., Sathish, M., & Das, M. R. (1999). A study on the distribution and ecology of phytoplankton in the Kuttanad wetland ecosystem, Kerala, India. *Pollution Research*, 18(3), 261-269.
- Ingole, S. B., Naik, S. R., & Kandam, G. (2010). Study of phytoplankton of freshwater reservoir at Majalgaon on Sindphana river, district Beed (M.S). *International Research Journal*, 1(13), 87-88.
- Javaid, A., & Ashok, K. (2012). Physicochemical characteristics of water in Wular Lake, a Ramsar site in Kashmir Himalaya.

- International Journal of Geology, Earth and Environmental Sciences*, 2(2), 257-265.
- Jyothi, K., & Narasimha Rao, G. M. (2013a). Seasonal distribution of phytoplankton in Raiwada Reservoir, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Nature and Science of Biology*, 5(3), 290-295.
- Jyothi, K., & Narasimha Rao, G. M. (2013b). Diversity and seasonal variation of phytoplankton in relation to physicochemical parameters in Thatipudi Reservoir, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Seaweed Research and Utilization*, 35(1&2), 211-219.
- Jyotsna, N., Subba Rangaiah, G., & Narasimha Rao, G. M. (2014). Seasonal variation of microalgae in relation to the physicochemical parameters of Karagam Lake, Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Journal of Algal Biomass Utilization*, 5(4), 68-73.
- Kadam, M. S., Pampawar, D. V., & Mali, R. P. (2007). Seasonal variations in different physicochemical characteristics in Masoli Reservoir of Parbhani district, Maharashtra. *Journal of Aquatic Biology*, 3(4), 671-676.
- Kodarkar, M. S., Muley, E. V., & Vasant Rao, A. (1991). Kukarpally-Hussain Sagar: Ecological studies on an industrially polluted stream and its impact on a freshwater lake in Hyderabad. *India Association of Aquatic Biologists (IAAB) Publication*, 1(1), 150.
- Kodarkar, M. S., Muley, E. V., & Vasant Rao, A. (1991). Kukarpally-Hussain Sagar: Ecological studies on an industrially polluted stream and its impact on a freshwater lake in Hyderabad. *India Association of Aquatic Biologists (IAAB) Publication*, 1(1), 150.
- Mahesh, K., Mishra, N., & Devendra, N. P. (2013). An assessment of the physicochemical characteristics of Bhamka Pond, Hanumana, Rewa district, India. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 2(5), 1781-1788.
- Munawar, M. (1970). Limnological studies on freshwater ponds of Hyderabad, India. The biosense distribution of unicellular and colonial phytoplankton in polluted and unpolluted environments. *Hydrobiologia*, 36(1), 105-138.
- Philipose, M. T. (1960). *Proceedings of the Symposium on Algae*. Indian Council of Agricultural Research.
- Philipose, M. T. (1967). *Chlorococcales*. Indian Council of Agricultural Research.
- Pradhan, P. (2023). Aquatic plants and algae in protected bodies of freshwater: Understanding biodiversity and ecological

- importance. *Journal of Agriculture*, 6(4), 106-108. [https://doi.org/10.37523/jagri.2023.6\(4\).106-108](https://doi.org/10.37523/jagri.2023.6(4).106-108)
- Prescott, G. W. (1984). *The algae: A review*. Koeltz Scientific Books.
- Ravish Varma, & Singh, G. P. (2010). Seasonal distribution of phytoplankton in Laddia Dam in Sikar District of Rajasthan. *Research Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 1(4), 366-369.
- Salve, B. S., & Hiware, C. J. (2006). Studies on water quality parameters of a minor reservoir, Nadergul, Ranga Reddy district, Andhra Pradesh. *Journal of Aquatic Biology*, 22(1), 118-122.
- Sanap, R. R., Pingle, S. D., Gunale, V. R., & Mohite, A. K. (2008). Chlorophyceae from Godavari River at Nashik (M.S.), India. *Indian Hydrobiology*, 11(1), 91-97.
- Setu, M. R. D. S., & Rao, G. M. N. (2016). Seasonal abundance of phytoplankton in relation to physicochemical features of Venkammacheruvu Veeraghattam, Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh, India. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*, 11(4), 295.
- Setu, M. R., Kaparapu, J., & Narasimha Rao, G. M. (2015). Microalgae population in mangrove habitats of Visakhapatnam, East Coast of India. *Journal of Algal Biomass Utilization*, 6(2), 5-10.
- Sharma, K. K., Nitasha, S., & Sarbeet, K. (2007). Some limnological investigations in Ban Ganga stream, Katar, Jammu and Kashmir State. *Journal of Aquatic Biology*, 22(1), 105-109.
- Smita, B. S., Shaji, C., & Bindu, L. (2010). Physicochemical and biological characterization of effluent from KMML (Kerala Minerals and Metals Limited) Tio₂ industry, Chavara, Kollam District, Kerala. *Journal of Phytology Research*, 23(1), 87-90.
- Smith, G. M. (1950). *The freshwater algae of the United States* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Tiwari, T. N., & Shukla, M. (2007). Algal biodiversity and trophic status of some temporary water bodies of Kanpur. *National Environmental Protection Technology*, 6(1), 85-90.
- Trivedi, R. K., & Goel, P. K. (1986). *Chemical and biological methods for water pollution studies*. Environmental Publications.
- Varsha, S. K. (2019). Study of seasonal algal diversity from Jawahar Tank, Nipani (Karnataka), India. *Journal of Lorafauna*, 25(1), 140-144. <https://doi.org/10.33451/lorafauna.v25ipp140-144>

Welch, P. S. (1986). *Limnology methods*. McGraw-Hill.

Wijewardene, L., Wu, N., Gimenez-Grau, P., Holmboe, C., Fohrer, N., Baattrup-Pedersen, A., & Riis, T. (2021). Epiphyton in agricultural streams: Structural control and comparison to epilithon. *Water*, *13*(1), 3443.

Wu, N., Dong, X., Liu, Y., Wang, C., Baattrup-Pedersen, A., & Riis, T. (2017).